

Relationship Between Optimism and Self-Regulation Among Higher Secondary School Students

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Abstract- This study investigated the relationship between optimism and self-regulation among higher secondary school students. Using a survey method, data were collected from 600 students from Malappuram and Kozhikode districts. Statistical analysis revealed a significant positive relationship between optimism and self-regulation ($r = .579, p < .01$). No significant differences were observed based on gender, locality, or school management. The findings suggest that optimism contributes positively to students' self-regulatory behaviors and educational outcomes.

Keywords- Optimism, self-regulation, higher secondary students, educational psychology, survey research.

I. Introduction

Optimism and self-regulation are two important psychological constructs that influence academic performance and personal development. Optimistic learners generally display confidence and persistence, whereas self-regulated learners actively manage their learning processes through planning, monitoring, and evaluation.

Optimism is a source of motivation. It is much easier to initiate action when we believe our actions will lead to positive outcomes. This is particularly important when we face obstacles that may tax our persistence. In the face of disappointments, optimism energizes continued actions, while pessimism leads to giving up. Churchill's famous quote that "a pessimist sees the difficulty in every opportunity; an optimist sees the opportunity in every difficulty. Optimism is perhaps best regarded as a personal resource that fosters resistance to distress Scheier, M.F., Weintraub, J.K. and Carver, C.S. (1986). Researchers have studied people facing a variety of challenging life situations and found that optimism is consistently linked to lower levels of personal distress, and pessimism to higher levels of distress. Research supports the value of an optimistic outlook in coping with a variety of negative life events. One reason optimists do better involves how they explain why bad things happen.

Optimism is a form of positive thinking that includes the belief that you are responsible for your own happiness, and that more good things than bad will continue to happen to you. Optimists believe that bad or negative events are rare occurrences, and that it is not their fault when something bad happens, but is due to something external. People who are optimists tend to focus on the positive side of things rather than the negative. Optimism is a trait that should become more common. Optimism has been proven to improve the immune system, prevent chronic disease, and help people cope with unfortunate news.

Self-Regulation and abilities are critical components of health, happiness and competence. Modern society is tough competition. The individual has to be ready to face the conflicting challenges. For that child should be trained to face the pressure of competition by overcoming all the difficulties which confront him in day to day life. Besides he has to live up to the parental expectations and also to achieve his own ambition. Under these stressful environmental conditions it is a challenge to become successful. It is here the importance of self regulated learning comes into prominence. Self regulated learners continue to learn independently throughout life. Self regulated learners have a combination of academic learning skills and self control that makes learning easier. They are more motivated; in other words, they have the skill and will to learn. Self-regulated learners transform their mental abilities, whatever they are, into academic skills (Zimmerman, 2007).

An optimistic person thinks positively with hope for the future. So he can regulate his activities. High self Regulation has been related to better personal adjustment and psychopathology, healthier relationships, enhanced social skills, fewer problems with addictive behaviors such as smoking and drug abuse.

II. Review of Literature

The term is originally derived from the Latin optimum, meaning "best". Being optimistic, in the typical sense of the word, is defined as expecting the best possible outcome from any given situation. This is usually referred to in psychology as dispositional optimism. Optimism is a form of positive thinking that includes the belief that you are responsible for your own happiness, and that more good things will continue to happen to you in the future. Ever heard the expression 'the glass is half full?' It usually refers to how optimistic people see the world.

Aggarwal, J. C. (1996). suggested that optimism is prevalent because it has adaptive utility. A substantial body of research now supports this but confirms that optimism is not without risk. This essay will examine definitions and components of optimism as a background to understanding the mechanisms by which it acts and then present research findings about benefits and harm.

Optimism is defined as a global expectation that more good (desirable) things than bad (undesirable) will happen in the future (Scheier and Carver, 1985). As a personality trait, it is presumed to be stable with little scope for change and is alternatively described as big optimism.

Sheldon and Lyubomirsky (2006) set out to answer this question with a four-week experimental study. In this study, students were asked to either count their blessings everyday or write about details of their lives. At two-week and four-week intervals, the participants completed "check-ups", in which they rated their levels of well-being, positive emotions, and negative emotions.

Hmieleski (2007) examined the relationship between dispositional optimism and experience on the performance of entrepreneurial managers. Optimists were found to

be more effective in stable environments and pessimists in dynamically unstable environments.

Ridley (1994) conducted research which described how teachers can transform self-regulated learning theory and research into classroom practice. Their study revealed that teachers should model self regulatory attitudes and behavior and incorporate certain strategies into their teaching, share control of the learning process and create a risk-taking climate.

Wolters and Pintrich (1998) examined the contextual difference in student motivation and self-regulated learning in seventh and eighth grade mathematics, social studies and English. Results revealed that the difference by subject area and gender in motivation and cognitive strategy use varies, but not in regulatory strategy use or academic performance; relations among these constructs was similar across the three subject areas.

Zimmerman (2000) emphasized self-regulation as a cyclical process involving forethought, performance, and self-reflection. Previous studies have reported positive associations between self-regulation and academic achievement. Research on optimism indicates that positive expectations regarding future outcomes enhance motivation and resilience.

Objectives of the Study

1. To determine the relationship between optimism and self-regulation.
2. To examine differences in optimism based on gender, locality, and school management.
3. To examine differences in self-regulation based on gender, locality, and school management.

III. Methodology

The present study is an attempt to study the Relationship between Optimism and Self Regulation of Higher Secondary School Students.

The study employed a normative survey method. The sample consisted of 600 higher secondary students from Calicut and Malappuram, were selected through stratified random sampling. Data were collected using the Optimism Scale (Koya & Haneefa, 2015) and Self-Regulation Scale (Noushad, 2008).

Preliminary Analysis

The important statistical properties of the scores on the variables under study were analysed as a preliminary step. The mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis were computed for the whole sample. The details of the statistics are presented in Table.

Table 1

The details of statistical constant of two variables Optimism and Self Regulation for total sample are presented in Table

	Optimism	Self Regulation
N	600	600
Mean	152.496	265.935
Median	153.00	265.00
Mode	153.00	264.00
Standard Deviation	14.218	17.342
Skewness	0.729	0.387
Kurtosis	2.221	3.269

The table 1 reveals that the measures of central tendency viz., mean, median, mode of the variable optimism and Self Regulation of the total sample are almost equal with slight variation only.

From the table it can be seen that Optimism mean is 152.496, median is 153.00, and mode is 153.00, itself. Self Regulation mean is 265.935, median is 265.00, and mode is 264.00, itself. Above the table it can be seen that mean, median, and mode of the variable of optimism and Self Regulation for the total sample are almost equal. The important statistical properties of the scores on the variables under study were analysed as a preliminary step. The mean, median, mode, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis were computed for the whole sample.

IV. Results and Discussion

Regulation can be considered as normally distributed among total samples. Mean, median, and mode of optimism for total samples are almost equal. Mean, median, and mode self regulation for total samples are almost equal. The value of optimism skewness is 0.729, which shows that the distribution is positively skewed. The value of kurtosis is 2.221, it is platykurtic. The value of self regulation skewness is 0.729 which shows that the distribution is positively skewed. The value of kurtosis is 3.269 the curve is platykurtic.

A graphical presentation of the distribution of the scores is also attempted to get a clear picture of Self regulation and optimism.

Correlation between Optimism and Self Regulation of Higher Secondary School Students

The collected data was analyzed to find out the coefficient of correlation between Optimism and Self Regulation of higher secondary school students for the total sample.

Table 2
 Correlation between Optimism and Self regulation of Higher Secondary school students

Variable related	Mean	SD	N	Coefficient of correlation	Level of significance
Optimism	152.496	14.218	600	0.579	0.01
Self regulation	265.935	17.342	600		

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level

Table 2 shows the coefficient of correlation between Optimism and Self regulation of higher secondary school students in the total sample. The coefficient of correlation obtained for the total sample is 0.579. The value obtained suggests that the relation between the variables is significant at 0.01 level as the 'r' is greater than the tabled value required for significance at 0.01 level. The magnitude and direction of 'r' indicate the existence of a moderate positive relationship between variables. If increasing Optimism there will increase Self Regulation. Hence it can be concluded that there exists a significant moderate and positive relationship between the variables Optimism and Self regulation for the total sample.

Gender Difference in Optimism and Self Regulation.

It is part of the analysis gender difference Optimism and Self regulation is analyzed and the details are given the table 3.

Table 3
 Data and results of 't' test for the means of Optimism on self regulation between Boys and Girls students

Variables compared	Groups Compared						t - value	Level of significance
	Boys			Girls				
	N1	M1	SD	N2	M2	SD		
Optimism	300	153.05	14.23	300	152.94	14.20	0.482	NS
Self regulation	300	267.08	16.56	300	265.48	18.10	1.13	NS

NS: Not significant

From the table 3 shows that the t value obtained for Optimism of Boys and Girls students is 0.482, which are less than 1.96, the tabled value required for significance at

0.05 level. Hence the mean difference in Self Regulation between Boys and Girls is statistically not significant.

The t value obtained for Self Regulation is 1.13 which are less than 1.96, the tabled value required for significance at 0.05 level. Hence the mean difference in Self regulation between Boys and Girls is statistically not significant.

So it can be concluded that boys and girls are identical in their Optimism and Self Regulation.

Locale Difference in Optimism and Self Regulation

It is the part of the analysis locale difference Optimism and Self regulation is analyzed and the details are given the Table 4.

Table 4
 Data and results of 't' test for the means of Optimism on Self Regulation between Rural and Urban students

Variables compared	Groups Compared						t - value	Level of significance
	Urban			Rural				
	N ₁	M1	SD	N ₂	M2	SD		
Optimism	30	152.45	14.23	30	151.94	14.20	0.439	NS
Self regulation	30	266.38	16.56	30	265.48	18.10	0.638	NS

NS: Not significant

From the table 4 shows that the t value obtained for Optimism of Rural and Urban students is 0.439, which are less than 1.96, the tabled value required for significance at 0.05 level. Hence the mean difference in Self Regulation between Rural and Urban is statistically not significant.

The 't' value obtained for Self Regulation is 0.638 which are less than 1.96, the tabled value required for significance at 0.05 level. Hence the mean difference in self regulation between Rural and Urban is statistically not significant. So it can be concluded that Rural and Urban students are identical in their optimism and self regulation.

Difference type of school in Optimism and Self regulation

It is the part of the analysis Government and Aided difference optimism and Self regulation is analyzed and the details are given the table 5

Table 5
 Data and results of 't' test for the means of optimism on Self regulation between Government and Aided school student.

Variables compared	Groups compared						t-value	Level of significance
	Government			Aided				
	N1	M1	SD	N2	M2	SD		
Optimism	300	153.05	14.23	300	151.94	14.20	0.953	NS
Self regulation	300	266.38	16.56	300	264.88	18.10	1.06	NS

NS : Not significant

From the table 5 shows that the t value obtained for Optimism of Government and Aided students is 0.953, which are less than 1.96, the tabled value required for significance at 0.05 level. Hence the mean difference in Optimism between Government and Aided is statistically not significant.

The t value obtained for Self regulation is 1.06 which are less than 1.96, the tabled value required for no significance at 0.05 level. Hence the mean difference in Self regulation between Government and Aided is statistically not significant. So it can be concluded that Government and Aided students are identical in their Optimism and Self regulation.

V. Conclusion

The study concludes that optimism is significantly associated with self-regulation among higher secondary school students. Educational institutions should develop programs that strengthen positive thinking and self-management skills.

Significance relationship was found between the variables, Optimism and Self regulation of higher secondary school students in the total sample. There is a positive moderately significant relationship in the case of the total sample. There was no significant difference in the mean scores of Optimism between male and female, urban and rural, and government aided higher secondary school students.

The pupils with moderate optimism exhibit moderate Self Regulation, they can manage self regulation. A possible major implication is that the teachers and parents should be made to become optimistic. It helps the children to manage their self regulation. Parent's and teacher's understanding and cooperation are necessary for this purpose.

Teachers should concentrate to develop Optimism among students. Provide moderate Optimism that will lead to emotional Self Regulation. Optimism leads to positive thinking that helps to mental health. Teachers can help students to become self regulated by offering challenging and interesting tasks which will stimulate student engagement. Self Regulation helps to manage their own affairs. Providing moderate

optimism helps to avoid emotional outburst. Common self regulation skills can be taught, learned and controlled.

Teachers should consider the individual differences of students' needs and interests. Teachers should encourage students' participation in the classroom activities. Students should be trained in self-regulatory learning processes as the ability. Teachers can encourage students to enhance optimism which will enhance self regulation and achievement.

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